

Contributing to Reactor Physics Competence: Collaborative Modelling and Simulation Training

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ABSTRACT

Bridging the gap between academic theory and industrial-grade Modelling & Simulation (M&S) requires practical immersion in multiphysics workflows. This paper presents a **trainer-centric** pedagogical framework designed to accelerate autonomy in high-fidelity reactor analysis. The methodology utilizes a progressive benchmark suite, advancing incrementally from simplified models to full-core coupled multiphysics problems using open-source and legacy codes. Via a "*fostering habits*" approach, we examine how modern collaborative environments can be repurposed as supervisory tools for real-time technical guidance and Verification & Validation (V&V). After describing the approach, a selection of examples extracted from several internships and doctoral projects is proposed for demonstrating improved trainee capability in handling production-level tools with reduced trainer overhead.

Keywords: Education and Training, Modelling and Simulation, Practical Exercises, Basic Physical Phenomena

1. INTRODUCTION

The nuclear energy sector is experiencing a renewed positive trend, faced with diverse technological choices ranging from full-scale Light Water Reactors (LWRs) in operation to the emerging landscape of Small and Advanced Modular Reactors (SMRs/AMRs) under development. Regardless of the reactor technology considered—varying in coolants, spectra, or fuels—robust Modelling and Simulation (M&S) is an essential component of modern nuclear engineering, covering design concept, optimization, and safety demonstration. Mastering M&S requires navigating multiple physical domains, including neutron transport, thermal-hydraulics, and structural mechanics, each demanding specific competencies and the management of complex computational tools. As highlighted by European initiatives, the preservation and further development of this high-level expertise through Education and Training (E&T) is critical to meet future human resource demands [1]. While academic institutions provide strong theoretical foundations, early-career engineers often face a steep learning curve when transitioning to the practical demands of industrial workflows, integrated software environments, and collaborative project contexts. Internships play a vital role in bridging this gap, offering a necessary guided introduction and mentoring. Drawing on extensive experience with Italian and French internships and Ph.D. candidates, this paper presents a *trainer-centric* pedagogical framework designed to accelerate autonomy in high-fidelity reactor analysis. It addresses the challenge of integrating trainees with heterogeneous backgrounds—ranging from pure physics to informatics—into productive activities within tight timeframes (typically six months for a Master thesis). To streamline this onboarding and support trainees at their specific learning stage, we developed an incremental multidisciplinary benchmark suite that is used as modular library of resources from which specific paths are selected

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based on the trainee's project. Grounded in international recommendations [2], [1], [3], the suite progresses from simplified conceptual scenarios—emphasizing physical comprehension, numerical setup, and data post-processing—to complex multiphysics cases. The exercises cover domains from neutronics (lattice to 3D core) to system thermal-hydraulics, leveraging both available literature and industrial experience. The adoption of modern collaborative tools further enhances this approach, allowing trainers to track progress and identify common stumbling blocks early. This provides insights into effective onboarding strategies while accelerating the trainee's path to fulfilling their objectives. After briefly presenting the pedagogical approach (Section 2), a selection of examples extracted from several internships and doctoral projects and based on different codes and physical problems are discussed to show how trainer insights enhance both student learning and program effectiveness (Section 3). Finally, Section 4 discusses possible extensions of this approach for academic collaborations and potential applications combined with sensitivity tools [4].

2. THE PEDAGOGICAL FRAMEWORK

The proposed *trainer-centric* pedagogical framework schematically represented in Figure 1 aims progressively integrate students into the complex academic and industrial environments. This structured approach aligns with European efforts (e.g., ENEN [1]) to preserve high-level expertise through targeted training.

Figure 1. Proposed learning path based on a "fostering habits" approach

Industrial workflows require navigating heterogeneous digital infrastructures (GED, shared repositories, mixed Linux/Windows platforms). By utilizing modern collaborative tools (Git, Python) and pre-existing guidelines, we significantly reduce "tool-setup" time, allowing the student to focus on physical comprehension and Verification & Validation (V&V) habits within the limited internship duration. This accelerates onboarding and mirrors the cooperative frameworks seen in large-scale European R&D projects [3, 2].

Technical competence is built on a "fostering habits" approach through an incremental multidisciplinary benchmark suite (Table I), drawing on authors' extensive R&D experience gained through participation in several International activities within industrial and research frameworks [2, 5]. The suite acts as a modular toolkit covering neutronics (lattice to 3D full-core) and thermal-hydraulics across diverse reactor concepts (PWR, VVER, SFR, LFR), fuels (UOX, MOX), and spectra. Each trainee follows a "critical

path" tailored to their specific topic (e.g., Lead-cooled Fast Reactors or PWR neutronics).

The diversity of the modular toolkit highlights the impact of physical assumptions and computational schemes while facilitating code-to-code comparisons and V&V activities using both standard deterministic *two-step* approaches and high-fidelity Monte Carlo methods [6, 7] with and without the support of statistical libraries, i.e. URANIE and OpenTURNS, as shown in [5]. Indeed, the tests available in the suite utilize a mix of legacy (e.g., APOLLO3® THEDI, ATHLET/RELAP5) and open-source codes (e.g., OPENMC, OpenModelica) as shown in Table II. Open-source tools offer flexibility, allowing asynchronous work on personal machines via various environments (clusters, Docker, WSL2) improving the learning curve. To ensure essential industrial competencies, modern workflows are enforced by requiring Python for data post-processing and Git for version control, fostering essential collaborative development skills.

		2D			3D	
		Cell	Fuel Assembly	Core	TH loop / System	
		Derived from available literature				
PWR	Neutro	UOX[8], MOX[9]	UOX[8], MOX[9]	UOX[8]	UOX[8]	-
VVER		UOX[8], MOX[10]	UOX[8]	UOX[8][6]	UOX[8][6]	-
SFR		MOX[11]	MOX[11]	MOX [11]	MOX[11]	-
LFR		MOX[12]	MOX[12]	MOX[12]	MOX[12]	-
PWR	TH	-	UOX[13]	UOX[13]	UOX[6][14]	-
VVER		-	-	UOX[6][7]	UOX[6][7]	UOX[15]
SFR		-	-	-	ESFR[16]	FFTF[17]
LFR		-	-	-	-	LM Loop[18]

Table I. Test matrix: cases available from previous publications

Lattice	N (core)	TH (core)	N/TH coupled	TH (system)	SA
APOLLO3®	APOLLO3®	DASSH	APOLLO3®THEDI	THEDI	URANIE
OPENMC	OPENMC		GENFOAM	ATHLET [19, 20]	OPENTURNS
SERPENT2	SERPENT2			RELAP5 [19, 20]	
TRIPOLI4®	GENFOAM			OpenModelica	

Table II. Some of the codes tested

3. OVERVIEW OF CASE STUDIES AND PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION RESULTS

The pedagogical approach described in Section 2 has been successfully applied to support numerous students during their initial immersion into the nuclear industry, primarily through Master's internships and Ph.D. research periods. Whether the student is working on traditional PWRs or advanced reactors (e.g. lead and sodium cooled fast reactors, LFRs and SFRs), the training workflow remains the same: progressing from simplified models to complex system behavior with the work supported by guidelines to transform the technical barriers they may initially have into standard professional reflexes early in their internship. The following sections present few examples selected to showcase the framework's versatility across different physical domains and reactor concepts.

3.1. On Neutronics Applications

The first set of applications presented concerns **lattice-level** analyses. Access to simplified 2D cell configurations, representing both LWRs and FRs concepts (Figure 2), enables students to explore calculation schemes, perform result analyses, and conduct code comparisons. Owing to their simplicity and short

computation times, these cases allow for the efficient evaluation of various modelling options—such as nuclear data libraries, meshing strategies, self-shielding treatments, and isotopic compositions—before progressing to more complex configurations.

Figure 2. Cell cases investigated in the paper [5, 21]

As shown in [22], this approach was applied to FRs studies using the APOLLO3® code [23]. Calculation options were first evaluated at cell and assembly levels before addressing cluster cases, such as those shown in Figure 3 and Table III, used for few-group control rod cross-sections preparation. This stepwise method streamlined the analysis, enabling trainees to manage a complex code as APOLLO3® and to perform several parametric studies and comparisons among FR concepts within a six months time-frame.

Figure 3. Cluster geometry for preparing control rod cross-sections [22]

	APOLLO3®		TR4[24]	OMC
JEFF	3.1.1	3.3	3.1.1	3.3
SSH	SgECCO	TONE	-	-
Sym.	one-twelve			full
Eg	1968	1760	cont.	
k_{∞}	1.05219	1.05168	1.05081	1.05469
$\Delta\rho$ [pcm]	-	-46	-125	225

Table III. Comparison for the 2D cluster results (OMC = OPENMC) [22]

The cell approach also facilitated initial verification for preparing cross-sections in APOLLO3®TrioCFD coupling exercises [25] based on PWR case. Simplified cell geometries were used to establish the coupling framework (see Par. 3.2). Cross-sections are prepared with the APOLLO3® lattice code and homogenized using different strategies, as indicated in Figure 4. The investigated PWR case, TVA WB1 [26], employs an Integral Fuel Burnable Absorber (IFBA) layer, necessitating specific self-shielding options. To verify these results, a comparison with SERPENT2 model based on the same test exercise was performed, as shown in Table IV.

Figure 4. Homogenization approach of a sub-channel [25]

Investigations extended beyond keff comparisons to include detailed cross-sections analyses, as shown in ref. [27] using the OPENMC (OMC) code. Reference [21] reports an example comparison of 1-group

	APOLLO3®	SERPENT2
KINF	1.00945	1.01129 ± 0.00022

Table IV. IFBA: comparisons between SERPENT2 and APOLLO3® [25]

equivalent cross-sections between APOLLO3® and OPENMC. This approach enabled efficient code-to-code and nuclear data library comparisons with limited additional effort.

The proposed exercises also allow students to progress to 2D and 3D **models at core level** (Figure 5). Various reactor concepts are available in the test matrix, where simplified models are used to analyze behavior under different boundary conditions (fuel and coolant temperature variations, assembly dilatation, voided conditions, etc.) and to calculate main reactivity coefficients (e.g., Figure 6 [5]). These coefficients can subsequently be adopted, for instance, in point kinetics (PK) models within the system codes [27, 21, 28, 29], see Par. 3.3.

Figure 5. 3D OPENMC core model [21]

Figure 6. Example of reactivity coefficient [5, 21]

3.2. Coupled Neutronics/Thermal-Hydraulics Applications at Core Level

The simplified cell approach proved crucial for establishing the coupling structure between APOLLO3® and TrioCFD [25]. Using computationally inexpensive cases allowed for efficient assessment of the coupling logic (Figure 7), spanning from cross-sections preparation and core-level geometry representation to field exchanges between codes. This initial phase enabled early integration of High-Performance Computing (HPC) compatibility and parallelization considerations. These foundations were essential for subsequently running more complex configurations capable of capturing realistic fluid path behaviors, such as a cluster with a central guide tube (Figure 8). Notably, strong emphasis was placed on workflow automation -specifically through Python pre-processing scripts for TrioCFD mesh generation - significantly reducing barriers for future applications [25]. A similar approach was also successfully tested for other coupling strategies (TRIPOLI5[30]/THEDI), as detailed in [31].

3.3. System Thermal-Hydraulics Applications

Another set of applications is related to the simulation of the flow conditions and the assessment of the initial transient behavior (e.g., using point kinetics). For this kind of application, a simplified loop model (Figure 9) is available in the test suite using OpenModelica (OM), based on previous works [19, 20, 18, 32]. This model was instrumental in investigating natural circulation phenomena [21, 28]. This model has been used as the basis of the activity carried out in ref. [29]. A test representing the loop (Figure 10) has been generated and integrated to the THEDI code (multi-1D TH code of CEA) for checking the implementation of heavy metal (lead bismuth and lead) properties and arriving to simulate a simplified Unprotected Loss of Flow (ULOF) transient.

Figure 7. The Coupling logic: a full Overview [25]

Figure 8. Vector plot of the velocity magnitude after the last spacer grid for a 3x3 cluster with TrioCFD [25]

Figure 9. Simplified system layout considered Open-Modelica [21]

Figure 10. Schematic representation of the simplified reactor model adopted for the THEDI simulation [29]

4. CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

Based on extensive experience with several internships and Ph.D. candidates, this paper has presented a **trainer-centric** pedagogical framework designed to accelerate autonomy in high-fidelity reactor analysis. The *fostering habits* approach is the pillar of the methodology for bridging the gap between academic preparation and professional practice within nuclear engineering.

Drawing on the authors' participation in numerous international industrial and research frameworks, an **incremental multidisciplinary benchmark suite** has been created and it acts as a modular toolkit from which each trainee may follow a **critical path tailored on the specific topic**. The practical experience gained adopting the proposed pedagogic approach has demonstrated enhanced learning efficiency, and deepened technical understanding of complex multiphysics reactor phenomena.

Future developments will aim to broaden this framework through the integration of complementary tools, such as sensitivity and uncertainty analysis platforms. The ultimate goal is to consolidate a sustainable training methodology that effectively aligns education, research, and industry needs within the rapidly evolving landscape of nuclear technologies.

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